

DESIGN, EXPRESSION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF R₁₀-SOD1 FUSION PROTEIN

Yi Wu¹, Hengwei Zhang², Xiaolu Wang², Chengyue Hu³, Lixiong Wu^{4*}, Renwang Jiang^{2*}

¹Zhongshan Torch Polytechnic, Zhongshan, Guangdong, China.

²College of Pharmacy, Jinan University, Guangzhou, Guangdong, China.

³School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Guangzhou University of Chinese Medicine, Guangzhou, Guangdong, China.

⁴Zhongshan Beiling Biotechnology Co. Ltd. Zhongshan, Guangdong, China.

Article Received on 29 March 2026,
Article Revised on 18 April 2026,
Article Published on 01 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19877622>

*Corresponding Author

Renwang Jiang

College of Pharmacy, Jinan University, Guangzhou, Guangdong, China.

How to cite this Article: Yi Wu¹, Hengwei Zhang², Xiaolu Wang², Chengyue Hu³, Lixiong Wu^{4*}, Renwang Jiang^{2*} (2026). Design, Expression And Characterization Of R₁₀-SOD1 Fusion Protein. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(5), 767-777.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) exhibits unique functions (e.g. antioxidation, radiation protection, and anti-aging), and has been widely applied in pharmaceutical, food, and cosmetic industries. SOD can be classified into three types based on its cellular localization, among which copper/zinc superoxide dismutase (SOD1) is the most widely distributed in tissues. Due to cellular and tissue barriers as well as the low permeability of biological membranes, exogenous SOD proteins cannot cross cell membranes, limiting their practical applications. In this study, a membrane-penetrating fusion protein— R₁₀-SOD1— was constructed and expressed through genetic recombination technology. This protein consists of human-derived copper/zinc superoxide dismutase (SOD1) fused with a cell-penetrating peptide containing 10 arginines (R₁₀). The research

encompasses the design and construction of the fusion gene, inducible expression in the *Escherichia coli* system, purification protocols for the recombinant protein, and functional evaluation of its membrane-penetrating capacity and antioxidant activity. The results demonstrate that the R₁₀-SOD1 fusion protein possesses favorable membrane-penetrating ability, and the *in vitro* enzymatic activity and antioxidant capacity are superior to those of

SOD1 alone. This study not only provides novel research tools for related fields but also establishes theoretical and technical foundations for the subsequent development of bioactive protein-based functional molecules.

KEYWORDS: antioxidation; copper/zinc superoxide dismutase; genetic recombination; membrane-penetrating ability; R₁₀.

1. INTRODUCTION

Free radicals (FR) are atoms or groups with unpaired electrons, representing normal metabolic products of the organism with strong oxidizing properties. The most extensively studied free radicals are reactive oxygen species (ROS).^[1] ROS generated during cellular metabolism, such as O₂ •⁻ and •OH, primarily originate from the mitochondrial electron transport chain. ROS plays crucial roles in maintaining cellular homeostasis. However, ROS can also serve as signaling molecules in aging, cardiovascular diseases, inflammation and cancer.^[2,4] External oxidative stressors, including radiation, ischemia, inflammation, and chemical agents, can elevate intracellular ROS levels, damaging cellular lipids, DNA, and proteins, leading to various diseases such as cancer, hypertension, diabetes and aging.^[5] Therefore, timely elimination of excess intracellular ROS is essential. The cellular antioxidant system maintains ROS at optimal levels.^[6] This system comprises antioxidant enzymes and small-molecule antioxidants, in which superoxide dismutase (SOD) is the most important class of antioxidant enzymes.

SOD is a metal-carrying antioxidant enzyme and a critical component of the antioxidant system. The antioxidant and catalytic functions of SOD were discovered by McCord and Fridovich in 1969.^[7] SOD catalyzes the dismutation of O₂ •⁻ into H₂ O₂ and O₂.^[8] H₂ O₂ is subsequently decomposed into H₂ O and O₂ by catalase (CAT). As the catalytic enzyme initiating the first step of antioxidation, SOD is particularly significant among numerous antioxidant enzymes. In mammalian cells, SOD can be classified into three types based on cellular localization: SOD1, encoded by a gene on chromosome 21, is a homodimer with a molecular weight of 32 kDa, primarily localized in the cytoplasm with minor presence in the mitochondrial intermembrane space and nucleus; SOD2, encoded by a gene on chromosome 6, is a homotetramer of 96 kDa, almost exclusively localized in the mitochondrial matrix; SOD3, encoded by a gene on chromosome 4, is a homotetramer of 135 kDa and serves as the major antioxidant enzyme secreted into the extracellular space.^[9] The active centers of SOD1 and SOD3 contain copper/zinc ions (Cu/Zn-SOD), whereas SOD2 contains manganese ions

(Mn-SOD).^[10] SOD1, formerly known as hemocuprein, was first characterized in 1969.^[7] SOD1 is the most widely distributed in tissues, accounting for 90% of total SOD.^[11] SOD1 is most notably recognized for its role in familial amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (FALS), where SOD1 mutations increase the propensity for SOD1 aggregation, leading to motor neuron death.^[12] SOD1 is also overexpressed in various cancers, including lung adenocarcinoma, non-small cell lung cancer, and 70% of primary breast cancers. SOD1 plays important roles in Type I interferon-driven hepatocyte oxidative injury,^[13] retinal cell oxidative damage.^[14] angiotensin II-induced chronic hypertension in rats,^[15] ischemic brain injury,^[16] spinal cord injury,^[17] non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) and alcohol-related liver disease.^[18]

In summary, SOD can be classified into three types based on cellular localization in mammalian cells, with SOD1 being the most widely distributed in tissues, accounting for 90% of total SOD.^[11] SOD eliminates excess intracellular ROS, and the cellular antioxidant system maintains ROS at optimal levels.^[6] However, endogenous SOD1 gradually decreases with age, necessitating timely supplementation with exogenous SOD1. Due to cellular and tissue barriers as well as the low permeability of biological membranes, exogenous SOD proteins cannot traverse cell membranes, limiting their practical applications. How can exogenous SOD exert its effects? Cell-penetrating peptides are required.

Cell-penetrating peptides (CPPs), also known as protein transduction domains, are short peptides capable of transporting proteins, peptides, and other biological macromolecules across mammalian cell membranes.^[19] The cell-penetrating peptide employed in this study is R₁₀, a short peptide containing 10 arginine residues. We constructed an R₁₀-SOD1 fusion protein expression vector through genetic recombination technology, induced its expression in *Escherichia coli*, and purified the recombinant protein. Subsequently, its biological functions were evaluated *in vitro*, including antioxidant activity and membrane-penetrating efficiency.

2. Expression and Purification of R₁₀-SOD1 Recombinant Protein

2.1 Construction of Recombinant Plasmid

- 1) Primers were designed to amplify the SOD1 fragment by PCR using LO2 cell cDNA as a template (Fig. 1A). The target fragment was recovered by gel extraction to remove salt ions from the product and analyzed by electrophoresis (Fig. 1B). The forward primer contained the SOD N-terminal sequence, R₁₀ sequence, a vector sequence, and a

restriction site, while the reverse primer contained the SOD C-terminal sequence, a vector sequence, a restriction site, and a 6×His tag sequence. The resulting SOD1 plasmid contained vector sequence, R₁₀ sequence, restriction sites and His-tag sequence, which could be subsequently recombined with the linearized vector PET15b bearing the same restriction sites.

- 2) The PET15b vector was double-digested with Nco I/Xho I to obtain the linearized vector (Fig. 1C).
- 3) The SOD1 plasmid and linearized vector were recombined using recombinase. Since the SOD1 plasmid contained Nco I/Xho I restriction site sequences and vector sequences, it could be recombined with the linearized plasmid digested with Nco I/Xho I under the action of recombinase.

Figure 1: Construction of R₁₀-SOD1 recombinant plasmid. (A) PCR amplification of SOD1 fragment with R₁₀-SOD1 fragment; (C) Electrophoresis of PET-15b plasmid after double digestion.

- 1) The recombinant plasmid was transformed into competent DH5α cells. Successfully recombined plasmids are circular and can enter *E. coli* competent cells after heat shock at 42°C. Since the PET15b vector carries ampicillin resistance, all *E. coli* cells that have successfully taken up the recombinant plasmid can grow as single colonies on plates containing ampicillin. In contrast, SOD1 fragments and linearized PET15b vector that failed to recombine cannot enter *E. coli* cells, and *E. coli* without ampicillin resistance cannot grow on ampicillin-containing plates.
- 2) Single colonies were picked from the plates for Sanger sequencing. Successful sequencing confirmed that the cell-penetrating peptide sequence and SOD1 sequence were correctly fused together. The sequencing results demonstrated that the R₁₀-SOD1 recombinant

plasmid was successfully constructed (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Partial sequencing results of R₁₀-SOD1 recombinant plasmid.

2.2 Expression of Recombinant Protein

The successfully sequenced plasmid was transformed into expression competent BL21 cells. Single colonies were picked for shake flask culture and scale-up cultivation. The inducer IPTG was added to induce target protein expression. The bacterial culture was collected by centrifugation, subjected to ultrasonic disruption, and centrifuged again to obtain the supernatant containing the target protein, which served as the crude enzyme sample. Coomassie brilliant blue staining was performed to detect whether the target protein was present in the crude enzyme. A relatively thick band was observed near 20 kDa, which was presumed to be the target protein (Fig. 3A). The molecular weight of SOD1 protein is 18 kDa, slightly smaller than that of SOD1 containing the cell-penetrating peptide. So, it migrated faster on the gel.

2.3 Purification of Recombinant Protein

Next, the expressed target protein was purified. Since the target protein contains a 6×His tag, NTA-nickel columns can recognize the 6×His tag. When the crude enzyme flowed through the nickel column, the target protein containing the His-tag bound to the column, while proteins in the crude enzyme without the 6×His tag flowed through directly. Impurities were further removed by washing. Finally, the target protein bound to the column was eluted using the high concentration of imidazole in the elution buffer. The eluted protein solution was placed in an ultrafiltration tube with a specific molecular weight cutoff (10 kDa), and the protein storage buffer was used for multiple exchanges and concentration to obtain the target protein with a certain concentration and relatively high purity.

The purified protein was further verified by Coomassie brilliant blue staining, which showed that relatively pure R₁₀-SOD1 protein was obtained (Fig. 3B), with a purity of approximately 90%. To further confirm whether these proteins were SOD1 proteins, Western blot analysis

was performed. First, SOD1-specific primary antibody was used for binding, followed by binding with horseradish peroxidase-labeled secondary antibody. Finally, the bands were exposed using chemiluminescence reagent. Bands of corresponding size were observed at the expected positions, indicating that the obtained protein was indeed SOD1 protein (Fig. 3C).

Through the above experiments, this study successfully constructed the R₁₀-SOD1 recombinant plasmid through PCR, enzyme digestion, recombination, and sequencing. Furthermore, the target protein was expressed, purified, and verified in expression competent cells, and finally, relatively pure R₁₀-SOD1 protein successfully obtained.

Figure 3: Expression, purification, and identification of R₁₀-SOD1 protein. (A) SDS-PAGE of crude R₁₀-SOD1 protein; (B) SDS-PAGE of R₁₀-SOD1 protein purified by nickel affinity chromatography; (C) Western blot verification of purified R₁₀-SOD1 and protein.

3. Enzymatic Activity Assay of R₁₀-SOD1 Recombinant Protein

After successfully obtaining the R₁₀-SOD1 recombinant protein, the next step was to determine whether these proteins possessed SOD1 enzymatic activity. The WST-1 method was employed. The results showed that R₁₀-SOD1 exhibited SOD1 enzymatic activity, which was stronger than that of SOD1 without the cell-penetrating peptide (Fig. 4A). Subsequently, the total antioxidant capacity of the obtained recombinant SOD1 protein was evaluated *in vitro* using the ABTS assay. The results indicated that the R₁₀-SOD1 recombinant protein demonstrated significant antioxidant capacity, which was also stronger than that of SOD1 without the cell-penetrating peptide (Fig. 4B).

Figure 4: (A) R₁₀-SOD1 exhibits enzymatic activity; (B) R₁₀-SOD1 protein possesses antioxidant capacity.

4. Membrane-Penetrating Ability of R₁₀-SOD1 fusion Protein

The membrane-penetrating efficiency of R₁₀-SOD1 protein was further compared with SOD1 without the cell-penetrating peptide serving as the control. VERO and HK-2 cells were first cultured to approximately 70% confluence, then SOD1 and R₁₀-SOD1 were added. After 30 min, cells were collected, lysed, and subjected to Western blot analysis. The results showed that no band was detected in the SOD1 group, indicating that SOD1 protein did not enter the cells, whereas R₁₀-SOD1 protein could enter the cells and exhibited strong membrane-penetrating ability (Fig. 5A, 5B).

Further immunofluorescence analysis was performed. If R₁₀-SOD1 could penetrate the cell membrane and reach the intracellular space, green fluorescence would be observed after incubation with SOD1 primary antibody and fluorescence-labeled secondary antibody. VERO and HK-2 cells were cultured to approximately 70% confluence, and SOD1 and R₁₀-SOD1 were added. After 30 min, cells were fixed and incubated with SOD1 antibody for imaging observation. The results were consistent with Western blot analysis. The R₁₀-SOD1 recombinant protein treatment group showed obvious green fluorescence, indicating strong membrane-penetrating ability of R₁₀-SOD1 (Fig. 5C).

Figure 5: (A) Western blot detection of R₁₀-SOD1 protein membrane-penetrating ability in VERO and HK-2 cells; (B) Quantitative analysis of Western blot results; (C) Immunofluorescence detection of R₁₀-SOD1 protein membrane-penetrating ability in VERO and HK-2 cells.

5. CONCLUSION AND PROSPECT

5.1 Conclusion

The innovative significance of this project lies in fundamentally breaking through the technical limitations of traditional antioxidation. Through innovative gene fusion technology, the efficient cell-penetrating peptide was organically combined with superoxide dismutase to obtain the R₁₀-SOD1 fusion protein, developing a bioactive protein with transmembrane delivery capability. This achievement realizes a revolutionary transformation of antioxidant components from "surface skin action" to "intracellular repair."

This technological breakthrough addresses the long-standing bottleneck of absorption efficiency that has plagued SOD applications, enabling active ingredients to cross biological barriers and directly reach the source of free radical production (the interior of cells) to exert their biological effects. Meanwhile, the study adopted an advanced synthetic biology technical route to establish a safe and controllable recombinant protein production system, completely avoiding the potential risks of traditional animal extraction processes, and providing a safer, more stable, and environmentally friendly technical solution for the production of bioactive raw materials.

5.2 Prospect

A large amount of preclinical data indicates that CPP-SOD1 can cross cellular and tissue barriers to reach various types of cells and tissues, including the blood-brain barrier. By scavenging reactive oxygen species, reducing lipid oxidation and cell apoptosis, increasing

intracellular antioxidant enzyme activity, inhibiting the NF- κ B/MAPK signaling pathway, and regulating the expression of related proteins, CPP-SOD1 exerts antioxidant effects and alleviates diseases associated with oxidative stress, such as Parkinson's syndrome, diabetes, arthritis, cardiac fibrosis, obesity, aging, and cancer pain. Although CPP-SOD1 has not yet entered clinical trials, it has shown promising application prospects in many preclinical experiments. For example,

TAT-SOD1 has demonstrated better efficacy than the clinical radioprotective drug amifostine.^[20,22] The ultimate goal of this research is to deliver CPP-SOD1 to specific cells and tissues of patients, providing targeted treatment. In addition, due to the free radical-scavenging function of antioxidant enzymes, CPP-SOD1 also has potential applications in cosmetic products. This study aims to combine CPP and SOD1 to form a more stable, specific, efficient, and non-toxic CPP-SOD1 variants.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project was supported by the key project of general Universities in Guangdong province of China (2024ZDZX2101).

REFERENCES

1. Tang Z., Wang H.Y., Guo D.M. Research progress on the regulation of antioxidants and free radicals on tumors. *Sichuan Medical Journal*, 2022; 43(9): 932-935.
2. Burgoyne J. R., Mongue-Din H., Eaton P., *et al.* Redox signaling in cardiac physiology and pathology. *Circulation research*, 2012; 111(8): 1091-1106.
3. Lei Y., Wang K., Deng L., *et al.* Redox regulation of inflammation: old elements, a new story. *Medicinal research reviews*, 2015P; 35(2): 306-340.
4. Chio I. I. C., Tuveson D. A. ROS in cancer: the burning question. *Trends in molecular medicine*, 2017; 23(5): 411-429.
5. Cross C. E., Halliwell B., Borish E. T., *et al.* Oxygen radicals and human disease. *Annals of internal medicine*, 1987; 107(4): 526-545.
6. Rhee S. G. H₂O₂, a necessary evil for cell signaling. *Science*, 2006; 312(5782): 1882-1883.
7. McCord J. M., Fridovich I. Superoxide dismutase: an enzymic function for erythrocyte (hemocuprein). *Journal of Biological chemistry*, 1969; 244(22): 6049-6055.
8. Fridovich I. Biological effects of the superoxide radical. *Archives of biochemistry and*

- biophysics*, 1986; 247(1): 1-11.
9. Marklund S. L., Holme E., Hellner L. Superoxide dismutase in extracellular fluids. *Clinica chimica acta*, 1982; 126(1): 41-51.
 10. Zelko I. N., Mariani T. J., Folz R. J. Superoxide dismutase multigene family: a comparison of the CuZn-SOD (SOD1), Mn-SOD (SOD2), and EC-SOD (SOD3) gene structures, evolution, and expression. *Free radical biology and medicine*, 2002; 33(3): 337-349.
 11. Pardo C. A., Xu Z., Borchelt D. R., *et al.* Superoxide dismutase is an abundant component in cell bodies, dendrites, and axons of motor neurons and in a subset of other neurons. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 1995; 92(4): 954-958.
 12. Kruman I.I., Pedersen W. A., Springer J. E., *et al.* ALS-linked Cu/Zn-SOD mutation increases vulnerability of motor neurons to excitotoxicity by a mechanism involving increased oxidative stress and perturbed calcium homeostasis. *Experimental neurology*, 1999; 160(1): 28-39.
 13. Bhattacharya A., Hegazy A. N., Deigendesch N., *et al.* Superoxide dismutase 1 protects hepatocytes from type I interferon-driven oxidative damage. *Immunity*, 2015; 43(5): 974-986.
 14. Dong A., Shen J., Krause M., *et al.* Superoxide dismutase 1 protects retinal cells from oxidative damage. *Journal of cellular physiology*, 2006; 208(3): 516-526.
 15. Collister J. P., Bellrichard M., Drebes D., *et al.* Over-expression of copper/zinc superoxide dismutase in the median preoptic nucleus attenuates chronic angiotensin II-induced hypertension in the rat. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 2014; 15(12): 22203-22213.
 16. Jiang Y., Brynskikh A. M., Devika S., *et al.* SOD1 nanozyme salvages ischemic brain by locally protecting cerebral vasculature. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 2015; 213: 36-44.
 17. Sugawara T., Lewén A., Gasche Y., *et al.* Overexpression of SOD1 protects vulnerable motor neurons after spinal cord injury by attenuating mitochondrial cytochrome c release. *The FASEB Journal*, 2002; 16(14): 1997-1999.
 18. Gopal T., Kumar N., Perriotte-Olson C., *et al.* Nanoformulated SOD1 ameliorates the combined NASH and alcohol-associated liver disease partly via regulating CYP2E1 expression in adipose tissue and liver. *American Journal of Physiology-Gastrointestinal and Liver Physiology*, 2020; 318(3): G428-G438.
 19. Wang F., Wang Y., Zhang X., *et al.* Recent progress of cell-penetrating peptides as new carriers for intracellular cargo delivery. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 2014; 174:

126-136.

20. Pan J., Su Y., Hou X., *et al.* Protective effect of recombinant protein SOD-TAT on radiation-induced lung injury in mice. *Life Sciences*, 2012; 91(3-4): 89-93.
21. Pan J., He H., Su Y., *et al.* GST-TAT-SOD: Cell Permeable Bifunctional Antioxidant Enzyme—A Potential Selective Radioprotector. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2016; 2016(1): 5935080.
22. Pan J., He H., Su Y., *et al.* In vivo radioprotective activity of cell-permeable bifunctional antioxidant enzyme GST-TAT-SOD against whole-body ionizing irradiation in mice. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*, 2017; 2017(1): 2689051.